

ISic3134

I.Sicily inscription 3134

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stucco

Object

painted wall

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S. Lucia

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI329750

1. □ Θεόκτιστος ναύκλη-
2. ρος Λύκιος ΚΟΛΛΥ. CA
3. ΔΟΝΑΔ. Φ . . . □
- 4.

Edition: PHI329751

1. . . . ναύκλη-
2. ρος Λύκιος κολλυγα ²⁶collega²⁶
3. Ιοναθα φ[ηκιτ]. □
- 4.

Edition: PHI329946

1. □ Θεόκτιστος ναύκλη-
2. ρος Λύκιος κολλυ (βιστή) ς ᾿Α-
3. δον (ος) ²⁷Α | δόν(ιδος)²⁷ ἀδ[ελ]φ[οί] □
- 4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645475

PHI 329750

PHI 329751

PHI 329946

Bibliography

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